

Studies in the synthesis of Quinoline Derivatives
Part VIII.** Synthesis of 4 : 3'-methylenebis-
 (2,2'-dichloro-4'-methylquinoline)
 Derivatives

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IN continuation of our work on reactivity of 4-Bromo-
 methyl-2-hydroxy and 4-Chloromethyl-2-chloroquinoline
 derivatives^{1,2,3}, we report here the con-
 densation of 4-chloromethyl-2-chloroquinoline and
 4-bromomethyl-2-hydroxyquinoline with sodium salt of
 acetoacetanilide in the presence of Dimethyl sulphoxide,
 to give α -2-chlorolepidinyl acetoacetanilide (Ia) and
 α -2-hydroxyepidinyl acetoacetanilide (Ib), respectively.
 It was observed that the condensation did not occur
 in the absence of DMSO. The structure of (Ia) was
 confirmed by NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 + acetone- d_6),
 δ , 2.3, singlet, 3H, for methyl group; 3.65, doublet,
 $J=8$ Hz, 2H, for $-CH_2$ -group; 4.25, triplet, $J=8$ Hz,
 1H, for $-CH$ -group; 3.25, singlet, 1H, for $-NH$ -group,
 which disappears on D_2O -exchange; 7.1 to 8.0,
 multiplet 9H, aromatic protons. It also shows the
 enolic proton at δ , 10.6 which disappears on D_2O -
 exchange, indicating that it partially exists in the
 enolic form (Ic). The lower value obtained for the
 methylene protons at δ , 3.65, in the spectrum is due
 to the additional deshielding effect of the carbonyl
 group as shown in the structure (Ia). On the basis
 of integration values of methyl, methylene and enolic
 protons, it is calculated that the percentage of enol
 content is 20%. This is supported by the IR of (Ia)
 which shows broad enolic band at 3250 cm^{-1} and
 broad ketonic band of enol at 1570 cm^{-1} . (Ia) and
 (Ib) underwent cyclization when reacted with conc.
 H_2SO_4 to give 4 : 3'-methylenebis-(2-chloro-2'-hydroxy-
 4'-methylquinoline) (IIa) and 4 : 3'-methylenebis-
 (2,2'-dihydroxy-4'-methylquinoline) (IIb) respectively.
 (IIa) and (IIb) when reacted with phosphorous
 oxychloride, gave the same 4 : 3'-methylenebis-(2,2'-
 dichloro-4'-methylquinoline), (IIc). The structure of
 (IIc) is also confirmed by NMR spectrum ($CDCl_3$),
 δ , 2.6, singlet, 3H, $-CH_3$ -group, 4.8, singlet, 2H,
 $-CH_2$ -group; 6.6, singlet, 1H, aromatic proton of
 quinoline ring at 3-position, 7.3 to 8.2, multiplet 8H,
 for aromatic protons.

Experimental

*General method for the synthesis of α -2-chloro-
 lepidinylacetoacetanilides*: Pulverised sodium (0.23 g.)
 in dry benzene, was added acetoacetanilide (1.77 g.)

and the mixture was refluxed for 5-6 hr. on water
 bath. 4-chloromethyl-2-chloroquinoline (2.2 g.) and
 Dimethyl sulphoxide (2.0 ml.) were added to the above
 reaction mixture. The whole reaction mixture was
 refluxed for 8-9 hrs. The reaction mixture was
 poured in water, the residue filtered off and washed
 with water and finally crystallized from benzene. The
 m. ps. and the analytical data are reported in Table 1.
 The yields of products varied from 70 - 80%.

4 : 3'-Methylenebis-(2-chloro-2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl-
 quinoline) derivatives (IIa): α -2-Chlorolepidinylaceto-
 acetanilide (3.5g.) was dissolved in conc. H_2SO_4
 (5.0 ml.) and heated for 90 min. at $80-90^\circ$ on water
 bath. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed
 ice, the residue was filtered off and crystallized from
 acetic acid. The m. ps. and the analytical data are
 reported in Table 2. The yields of products varied
 from 70-80%.

4 : 3'-Methylenebis-(2,2'-dichloro-4'-methylquino-
 line) derivatives (IIc): The above (IIa), (1.0 g.) was
 heated with phosphorous oxychloride (3.0 g.) on an
 oil-bath at $110-15^\circ$ for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture
 was cooled and poured on crushed ice and the products
 crystallized from benzene. The m. ps. and analytical
 data are reported in Table 2. The yields of products
 varied from 40-50%.

**R. J. CHUDGAR and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 49 (for the previous part VII).

TABLE I

Ar	R	X	m.p.	Found %				Molecular Formula	Required %			
				C	H	N	Cl		C	H	N	Cl
Ph	H	Cl	157	68.58	5.05	7.48	10.00	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ O ₂	68.10	4.82	7.94	10.08
Ph	H	OH	265	71.52	5.21	7.94	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	71.86	5.39	8.39	—
<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	H	Cl	199	68.36	5.48	7.15	10.10	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	63.75	5.18	7.64	9.68
<i>o</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	H	Cl	178	65.95	4.91	7.76	9.17	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	65.88	4.96	7.32	9.28
<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	H	Cl	189	65.73	5.11	7.80	9.03	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	65.88	4.96	7.32	9.28
<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	H	OH	240	69.64	5.49	7.84	—	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	69.23	5.49	7.69	—
<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	Cl	166	61.70	4.54	7.71	18.55	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	62.01	4.13	7.23	18.35
<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	OH	233	65.06	5.02	7.29	10.00	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	65.13	4.61	7.60	9.63
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	Cl	185	61.90	4.53	7.06	17.29	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	62.01	4.13	7.23	18.35
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	OH	265	64.90	4.84	7.26	9.55	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	65.13	4.61	7.60	9.64
<i>p</i> -Br ₆ H ₄	H	Cl	187	55.37	3.57	6.44	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ BrCl	55.61	3.70	6.49	—
<i>α</i> -C ₁₀ H ₇	H	Cl	200	72.05	4.99	6.92	8.54	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	71.57	4.72	6.96	8.82
<i>α</i> -C ₁₀ H ₇	H	OH	280	74.82	5.34	7.09	—	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	5.21	7.29	—
Ph	CH ₃	OH	242	72.05	5.62	7.99	—	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	72.42	5.74	8.05	—
Ph	CH ₃	Cl	185	68.54	5.45	7.52	10.09	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ Cl	68.75	5.18	7.64	9.68
<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	Cl	195	69.18	5.12	7.32	9.55	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	69.38	5.52	7.36	9.33
<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	OH	274	72.69	6.26	6.98	—	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	72.94	6.08	7.74	—

TABLE 2

R ₁	R	X	Y	m. p.	Found %				Molecular formula	Required %			
					C	H	N	Cl		C	H	N	Cl
H	H	OH	OH	>360	75.56	5.18	8.22	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	75.96	5.06	8.85	—
H	H	Cl	OH	300	71.30	4.47	8.32	10.93	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ OCl	71.76	4.48	8.37	10.62
H	H	Cl	Cl	210	68.06	3.82	7.89	20.56	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	68.00	3.96	7.93	20.11
6-MeO	H	OH	OH	>360	72.38	4.98	7.91	—	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	72.84	5.20	8.09	—
6-MeO	H	Cl	OH	291	68.89	5.07	7.32	9.51	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	69.13	4.66	7.68	9.47
8-MeO	H	Cl	OH	296	69.63	4.58	8.01	9.39	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	69.13	4.66	7.68	9.74
7-Cl	H	OH	OH	>360	68.69	4.04	7.64	10.50	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	68.47	4.28	7.99	10.13
7-Cl	H	Cl	OH	315	64.87	4.41	7.84	19.70	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ OCl ₂	65.05	3.79	7.59	19.20
7-Cl	H	Cl	Cl	249	61.51	3.55	7.25	27.10	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl ₃	61.93	3.35	7.23	27.47
6-Cl	H	OH	OH	>330	68.60	4.56	7.59	10.56	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	68.47	4.28	7.99	10.13
H	CH ₃	OH	OH	>360	73.77	5.49	8.19	—	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	73.37	5.45	8.49	—
H	CH ₃	Cl	Cl	228	68.72	4.68	7.88	19.55	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ Cl ₂	68.66	4.36	7.63	19.35
8-Me	CH ₃	OH	OH	>360	76.35	5.65	8.00	—	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	76.74	5.81	8.14	—
8-Me	CH ₃	Cl	Cl	205	69.08	4.60	7.87	18.55	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ Cl ₂	69.30	4.73	7.35	18.64
Benzo (h)	H	OH	OH	>360	79.01	5.10	7.82	—	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	78.69	4.92	7.65	—
Benzo (h)	H	Cl	OH	>360	75.08	4.63	7.16	9.50	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ OCl	74.90	4.42	7.28	9.23
Benzo (h)	H	Cl	Cl	271	71.74	4.23	6.92	17.55	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₂	71.46	3.97	6.95	17.62

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